

MEDICAL SCIENCES

THE GAME IS UNDERGOING A TRANSFORMATION: APTOS VAGINAL THREADS FOR THE TREATMENT OF STRESS URINARY INCONTINENCE

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Abstract

Objective:

This study aimed to evaluate the efficacy of P(LA/CL) intimate threads in treating stress urinary incontinence (SUI) in women, focusing on symptom resolution, patient safety, and complication rates.

Materials and Methods:

A retrospective case series was conducted involving 23 women aged 34 to 53 with confirmed SUI. P(LA/CL) intimate threads, specifically Intimate Excellence Method (IEM) and Light Lift Spring Method Soft (LLSS) threads, were inserted into the anterior vaginal wall using local anesthesia. Patients were followed up at one week and three months post-procedure. The efficacy was assessed through the Questionnaire for Urinary Incontinence Diagnosis (QUID), cough tests, and bladder ultrasonography.

Results:

Of the 23 women treated, 19 achieved complete resolution of SUI symptoms, while four experienced mild symptom improvement. Two patients exhibited mild urinary leakage during the third-month follow-up cough test. No significant complications were observed, and all patients were able to resume daily activities immediately after the procedure. The treatment demonstrated high effectiveness across different SUI severities (Grade 1–3).

Conclusion:

P(LA/CL) intimate threads provide a safe, minimally invasive alternative for treating stress urinary incontinence, with a high success rate and minimal downtime. This treatment may offer a viable non-surgical option for women with SUI, including those with severe symptoms.

Keywords: threads, stress urinary incontinence (SUI), Poly L-Lactic acid, Aptos Threads.

Introduction

Stress urinary incontinence (SUI) is an unintentional release of urine that occurs when coughing, sneezing, or engaging in physical activity. This is a prevalent issue that affects women once they have reached the age of 40. The incidence of stress urinary incontinence SUI ranges from 4% to 35%, and this rate tends to rise with aging.¹ Parity, obesity, age, and smoking are established risk factors for SUI.¹ SUI results in social and psychological issues for women and impacts their lifestyle.² Due to the global aging of the population, SUI exerts socioeconomic pressure. Researchers and physicians are trying to come up with an effective treatment. Patients have the option to undergo either non-surgical or surgical procedures. Non-invasive treatments may require a significant amount of time and effort from patients, and may also result in low treatment efficacy. Multiple surgical interventions are detailed, with the majority exhibiting elevated rates of complications and adverse effects. Novel research specifically addresses underlying molecular causes of SUI. This research primarily targets tissue components such as collagen and elastin, as well as factors related to nerve regulation and muscle function.³ Additionally, cell therapy is being explored as a potential treatment approach.³ Nonconventional, minimally invasive therapies are increasingly being used for the treatment of SUI.⁴ The current surgical treatments aim to rectify the inadequate angle of the urethra and bladder, with the objective of addressing the excessive mobility of the urethra. The most often used method to address SUI is

to elevate the bladder neck by creating a hammock using mesh.⁴ The objective is to provide assistance to the pubourethral ligament and alter the angle of the urethrovesical junction. Even though this traditional technique is widely utilized in operating rooms, patients do not always provide positive feedback. This failure may be attributed to the cause, and the procedure of SUI correction and not only to the abnormality in the pubourethral ligament. Yang et al. provide evidence that various anatomical factors contribute to the formation of SUI.⁵ The urethral mucosa possesses a sealing property that is compromised in individuals with SUI. The researchers also found that the integrity of the urethral sphincter, the elastic nature of the urethral wall, and the greater length of the functional urethra are crucial for the proper functioning of the urethra and the prevention of urine leakage. Tomatze et al. conducted a comparative analysis of MRI data of the pelvic floor before and six months after the installation of Aptos intimate threads for the treatment of SUI and their findings were in line with those of Yang et al.⁶ The researchers observed that following the Aptos intimate placement, there was an increase in the thickness and volume of the urethral mucosa and muscles. It was seen that the urethra became narrower, with thicker walls, and there was a noticeable increase in density within the inter-urethra-vaginal gap. Aptos intimate threads effectively addressed urethral abnormalities at both the molecular and physical levels, resulting in a high success rate in the treated group.⁶

More physicians incorporate technologically advanced treatment modalities such as laser, exosome, and stem cells into their practices on a daily basis. The Aptos intimate vaginal threads for SUI is an innovative method that has the potential to revolutionize the treatment of this problem.

Materials and Methods

Ethical Considerations

The study received approval from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of Ebru Unal Clinic. All patients provided written informed consent before participation, and the study was conducted in accordance with the 1975 Declaration of Helsinki as revised in 2000.

Patient Demographics

In this retrospective study, a total of 23 women were treated in 2022 and 2023 for complaints related to SUI. All patients provided written informed consent before participation and a cough test was carried out to confirm the presence of SUI in patients. The Questionnaire for Urinary Incontinence Diagnosis (QUID) was administered both prior to and three months following the procedure. (Figure 1) The patients' ages ranged from 34 to 53, and their BMI was between 21-27. Two patients were nulliparous, while all the remaining others had a history of vaginal delivery. One patient underwent a hysterectomy; three had vaginal laser treatment, and one tried radiofrequency treatment for SUI, but did not experience a favorable outcome. The severity of SUI was assessed using the Ingelman-Sundberg scale: Urinary incontinence of Grade 1 was identified as being triggered by coughing or sneezing, Grade 2 urinary incontinence was triggered by jogging or bending down to pick up an object from the floor, and Grade 3 urinary incontinence was triggered by walking or climbing stairs.⁷(Figure 2) Ten patients had Grade 3 SUI, and they experience daily episodes of urine leakage, necessitating the usage of pads. Women with an ongoing vaginal infection, current pregnancy, bleeding condition, aspirin intake, or severe pelvic organ prolapse (Stage 3 or higher according to the Pelvic Organ Prolapse Quantification Scale) were excluded from the treatment.⁸ All women included in the treatment experienced either Stage 1 or Stage 2 Pelvic Organ Prolapse.

The instrument

Aptos threads consist of Poly-L-Lactic Acid and Poly Caprolactone P(LA/CL). Poly L-lactic acid has a bio-stimulatory effect on the tissue, while Polycaprolactone is accountable for the extended duration of Poly L-lactic acid in the tissue, lasting for 24 months. Intimate Excellence Method (IEM) and Light Lift Spring Method Soft (LLSS) threads are utilized for the treatment of SUI. IEM is a type of absorbable thread with multi directional barbs. Its distinctive characteristic is that it amplifies the strength of tissue integrity. Inserting multidirectional barbs can enhance the distribution, stress resistance, and grip of soft tissues. The efficient design of IEM involves approximating the entire treatment region using a straightforward and noninvasive approach. Threads are placed through a cannula with a round tip that minimizes bleeding and edema following the surgery. Light Lift Spring Method Soft (LLSS) is the second thread used in the procedure which has a blunt-tipped cannula encircled by a spirally coiled

thread. The flexibility and form of LLSS remain intact after insertion. When LLSS is introduced into the vaginal tissue, it promotes the creation of collagen and creates new, healthy vaginal mucosa.

The procedure

Aptos intimate threads were inserted into the anterior vaginal wall, positioned in between the urethra and the vaginal mucosa, to treat SUI. The patients were instructed to empty their bladder immediately prior to the treatment. The procedure was performed using local anesthesia without any prior administration of premedication. Following the administration of local anesthetics to the front part of the vaginal wall, two clamps were used to secure the area located 1.5 cm away from the opening of the urethra in order to stabilize the anterior vaginal wall. An 18-gauge needle was used to penetrate the vaginal mucosa, creating an entry point for the threads, which were inserted through this access point. First, IEM was used. From left to right of the anterior vaginal wall, five IEM threads were placed in a parallel direction. The threads were inserted into the vaginal canal with a length of 8 cm. Two LLSS threads were positioned beneath the urethra, while the other two were placed on the left and right sides of the urethra. The threads formed upward pressure on the bladder neck, securing the urethra and imitating the vesicovaginal fascia, which reinforced the vaginal wall. If necessary, the 4.0 rapid vicryl is used to ensure the closure of the access point. The mean duration of the procedure was 25 minutes. Following the treatment, patients were advised to resume their normal daily activities while refraining from engaging in sexual intercourse for two weeks.

Assessment

The patients were examined at one week and three months post-procedure. None of the patients experienced any issues associated with Aptos intimate threads, and they reported that the resolution of incontinence began immediately. On the day of the procedure, every patient was able to urinate without the need for bladder catheterization. During the third month's appointment, all patients had a cough test. The bladder was assessed with vaginal ultrasonography. Upon observing that the bladder contained approximately 200cc of urine, the patients were instructed to cough. Two patients experienced urinary leakage during the cough test. According to QUID, four out of the 23 patients reported that they experienced mild-level SUI even after the insertion of Aptos threads. (Figure 3) One patient had undergone a procedure in 2022 and then received another Aptos threads insertion in 2023. After the second process, she was completely dry. Nineteen patients reported experiencing a total resolution of their symptoms. (Table 1) Before the procedure ten patients had reported urgency, which was subsequently resolved. Five patients reported experiencing nocturia, waking up three or more times during the night to urinate. This issue was also improved after thread implantation.

Discussion

Given its high prevalence among premenopausal and menopausal women, researchers and physicians are actively seeking a remedy for SUI. Surgical and non-surgical treatments are both methods implemented in

clinical practices. Women with minimal or mild symptoms, or those who are unable to endure the surgical criteria or may not be able to tolerate surgery, are recommended to engage in Kegel exercises, which necessitate a prolonged duration. However, the success rate for treating SUI using Kegel exercises over a period of 12 months is 58.8%.⁹ TOT and TVT were identified as gold-standard for surgical corrections of SUI.¹⁰ Unfortunately, the utilization of pelvic sling meshes for the treatment of SUI was prohibited by the FDA due to its complications and side effects.¹¹ Despite the off-label application of mesh and the woman's acceptance of procedure risks, the failure rate of TOT is 37.5% at the 3-year follow-up.¹² Hospitalization is required for all surgical treatments of SUI, which involve problems such as bladder laceration, urethral laceration, hemorrhage, mesh rejection, dyspareunia, and other issues. In addition, they may lead to a delayed overactive bladder. Women exhibit reluctance towards undergoing surgical operations due to their apprehension of the potential lack of desired outcomes following conventional surgical interventions for SUI.¹³ Numerous therapy options have been proposed, but unfortunately, there is a lack of standardization for measuring outcomes and assessing the efficacy instruments.¹⁴ Rovner et al. established the concept of the 'ideal treatment option' as one that is 100% effective and long-lasting, as well as being simple, fast, and easy to perform. It should also be minimally invasive and fully reversible, suitable for all types of SUI, and have low rates of morbidity and complications. Additionally, it should be affordable for patients, healthcare facilities, and the healthcare system as a whole.¹⁵

Novel therapeutic approaches for the management of SUI are currently being investigated. Li et al. revealed that the expression levels of integrin $\beta 1$ (also known as CD29), TGF- $\beta 1$, and type I collagen are reduced in the tissue samples obtained from the vaginal

wall of patients with SUI compared to samples obtained from non-SUI donors.¹⁶ Harland et al. highlight new treatments for SUI that increase TGF-beta in the vaginal mucosa, thereby promoting the synthesis of collagen types 1 and 3. Elevating the levels of collagen type 1 and 3 will enhance both the structural integrity of the tissue and the functionality of the urethral muscles.¹⁷ In their work, Cho et al. demonstrated that the addition of PLLA-PCL under the rat skin resulted in an elevation of TGF1, Collagen 1, and Collagen 3 levels after three weeks.¹⁸ Aptos intimate threads have a stimulating impact on collagen type 1 and 3 in the vaginal mucosa, which helps correct SUI. Based on our observations and the literature, bio stimulating effect of Aptos intimate threads improve the integrity of the urethral mucosa and enhances the functioning of the urethral muscles.

The learning curve for placing Aptos intimate threads for SUI is simple and fast. A surgical setup is not necessary as the procedure can be conducted in outpatient settings without any interruption. The installation of Aptos intimate threads is a more cost-effective option compared to any surgery for SUI, and its effects are immediately apparent. Tomatze reported that after a 3-year follow-up, all treated patients were completely free of symptoms related to SUI. However, additional trials are required to assess the durability of the treatment. Alternatively, reapplying the threads is a simple and efficient choice for patients experiencing SUI recurrence following the Aptos intimate threads surgery. Based on our clinical experience and findings, we can confidently assert that Aptos intimate threads for SUI represent a groundbreaking and transformative treatment option. They are an ideal alternative treatment for SUI that can be recommended to women of all ages regardless of their number of pregnancies.

Table 1.

QUID before and after the procedure

	Before	After
When you cough or sneeze	23	2
When you bend down or lift something up	10	0
When you walk quickly, jog or exercise	10	2

Figure 1: Questionnaire for Urinary Incontinence Diagnosis results of patients

Figure 2: Grouping of patients regarding SUI according to Ingelman-Sundberg scale

Walk Quickly, Jog or Exercise

Figure 3: QUID after the surgery

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